

12 November 2025

Press Release

SUN-DT Project Kicks Off to Advance the Digital Future of CSP Tower Plants

The Horizon Europe project **SUN-DT** (“*Smart Use of Novel Digital Tools for advanced performance and reduced costs in CSP tower plants*”) kicked off with a successful consortium meeting on **7-8 October 2025**, hosted by the project coordinator **CENER** at its headquarters in Sarriguren, Spain.

The **SUN-DT consortium** brings together **nine organisations from Spain, Germany, Turkey, and Belgium**, leveraging their complementary expertise in **Concentrated Solar Power (CSP)**, **digitalisation**, and **communications**, to advance the digital transformation of the CSP tower plants sector and thus increase its competitiveness in Europe.

The two-day kick-off meeting marked the official launch of project activities, gathering all consortium partners to align on objectives, methodologies, workplan and upcoming milestones. Coordinated by CENER, project partners exchanged views on technical aspects, coordination procedures and dissemination strategies to ensure an effective start to this ambitious project.

SUN-DT specifically aims to boost the competitiveness of the European CSP tower plants sector through **digital innovation**. Project partners will jointly advance and integrate **four interoperable innovative digital tools**:

- **HELIOSTATACC**: a heliostat automatic calibration and characterisation tool
- **SUN-DTWIN**: a Digital Twin of the solar field and receiver for automated decision-making
- **D-OPT**: an energy management system for dispatch optimisation system based on weather, and market and auxiliary services forecasts
- **PREDOM**: a predictive operation and maintenance (O&M) tool

These tools will be integrated into a unified **SUN-DT Platform**, which will be **tested and validated** at **two experimental facilities** and **two commercial plants**: the **Khi Solar One** plant in South Africa and the **Cerro Dominador** plant in Chile. These commercial CSP plants are operated by two consortium partners and global solar energy leaders, COX and ACCIONA respectively, representing different CSP tower configurations.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Disclaimer:

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement no 101234781. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project Information

Grant Agreement no.	101234781
Project name	Smart Use of Novel Digital Tools for advanced performance and reduced costs in CSP tower plants
Project acronym	SUN-DT
Type of action	HORIZON Innovation Actions
Topic identifier	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-01
Starting date	01 October 2025
Duration	36 months
EU contribution	€ 2.995.445,97

SUN-DT Coordinator	
CENER	FUNDACION CENER
SUN-DT Partners	
DLR	DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FUR LUFT - UND RAUMFAHRT EV
CIEMAT	CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES ENERGETICAS MEDIOAMBIENTALES Y TECNOLOGICAS
IME	FUNDACION IMDEA ENERGIA
INAVITAS	INAVITAS ENERJI ANONIM SIRKETI
ACCIONA	ACCIONA CONSTRUCCION SA
COX	COX ENERGY EPC S.L.
ESTELA	EUROPEAN SOLAR THERMAL ELECTRICITY ASSOCIATION
IMN	FUNDACION IMDEA NETWORKS

To stay up-to-date on SUN-DT's activities and news, follow the project on:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/sun-dt/>
- X (formerly Twitter): https://x.com/SUN_DT_Project

Project Coordinator contacts:

- Marcelino Sánchez (CENER) – msanchez@cener.com
- Amaia Mutuberria (CENER) – amutuberria@cener.com

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Disclaimer:

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement no 101234781. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.